

How Beginner and Non-Technical Users Perceive Web Accessibility Tools: A Comparative Study

Navdeep Kaur

Software Support engineer & MCA student

Independent Researcher

Chandigarh University (Punjab, India)

Author: Navdeep Kaur(navidhillon2019@gmail.com)

ABSTRACT

This paper evaluates the usability of popular web accessibility testing tools for users with little to no experience in accessibility testing. Even though not every website is completely accessible, developers should try to make their sites as inclusive as possible right from the start. Accessibility tools assist in locating possible problems that might hinder the efficient use of web content by individuals with disabilities. This study focuses on three widely used tools: the WAVE browser extension, the Axe DevTools, and Google's Lighthouse. It investigates how user-friendly these tools are and whether beginner web developers and non-technical users can benefit from them. To support this, feedback was collected from participants and analyzed to draw meaningful conclusions about the tools' usability.

1. INTRODUCTION

The internet has become an essential component of everyday living in the current digital era. Websites provide convenience that has replaced many conventional methods, whether it is ordering food, accessing educational materials, or obtaining information about a place. However, different people have different experiences with the web. When attempting to access digital content, people with disabilities often face significant barriers.

Around 314 million individuals worldwide are estimated to be visually impaired, with 45 million of them being totally blind [1]. Web accessibility aims to ensure that these individuals can perceive, understand, navigate, and interact with the web, just like everyone else [2]. It is not just for users with disabilities; older

persons and even those without disabilities can face comparable difficulties. [3] [4].

Making websites usable by individuals with a range of abilities and limitations is known as web accessibility. If a website is usable by individuals with disabilities just as well as by those without, it is deemed accessible [5].

In this study, I evaluated the usability of three popular web accessibility testing tools:

1. WAVE [6]
2. Axe DevTools [7]
3. Lighthouse [8]

These tools are commonly used by developers to detect accessibility issues, but their usability for beginner web developers and non-technical users

remains largely unexplored. This paper aims to assess how easily these users can interact with such tools, identify accessibility issues, and gain insights from the results. Feedback was collected from participants, and the findings are discussed in detail.

2. RELATED WORK

A number of research have been carried out to assess the effectiveness and usefulness of automated accessibility assessment tools as well as understand the broader challenges associated with implementing web accessibility.

Nguyen (Western Washington University) [9] conducted a comparative study of five automated accessibility evaluation tools (AAETs) including WAVE, Axe DevTools, Lighthouse, SiteImprove, and Microsoft Accessibility Insights. The study examined success criteria, test coverage, and reporting differences, introducing the concept of a Coverage Error Ratio (CER) to prioritize tools that better detect WCAG Level A violations. It was found that tools differ in focus—while SiteImprove had broader coverage, WAVE emphasized critical issues but missed less severe ones. The study also highlighted limitations in weighting WCAG levels and recommended adapting evaluation based on user needs and context.

Abuaddous et al. (University Sains Islam Malaysia) [10] investigated the difficulties in putting web accessibility into practice, breaking the study down into three areas: following rules and regulations, being careful while developing, and the limitations of both automated and user testing while assessing. The authors concluded that lack of awareness, motivation, and adequate training among developers significantly hinders accessibility compliance.

Kelly et al. introduced the concept of Web Adaptability, critiquing the limited impact of strict adherence to WCAG/ATAG/UAAG guidelines [11]. They proposed a more flexible and inclusive approach that factors in emerging technologies, varying definitions of accessibility, and institutional challenges. Their work moves the discussion beyond rule-based compliance towards practical adaptability in real-world web environments.

These studies highlight the technical capabilities of existing tools, the limitations in developer understanding, and the importance of context-driven accessibility evaluation. The purpose of this study is to fill the knowledge gap on the actual usefulness of these technologies from a non-technical standpoint, as well as the difficulties faced by novice web developers and non-expert users.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Participants

This usability study involved participants from diverse backgrounds including MCA students. Total 8 participants completed the study. Their experience levels with web development ranged from no experience to significant experience, allowing for an inclusive evaluation across varying levels of technical familiarity. The study intentionally included both technical and non-technical participants to assess the accessibility tools' ease of use from different user perspectives.

3.2 Tool Overview

Three popular accessibility testing tools were the subject of the study:

- **Axe DevTools:** A developer-focused browser extension integrated with Chrome DevTools. It provides detailed issue reports, often referencing HTML code and ARIA attributes. While powerful, its technical nature makes it more suited for users with a development background.

Figure 1. Axe DevTools panel within browser Developer Tools, displaying categorized issues with severity levels.

- WAVE (Web Accessibility Evaluation Tool): A browser extension that provides visual feedback by overlaying icons and indicators directly on the webpage being tested. It facilitates the detection of accessibility problems including poor contrast, missing alt text, or structural HTML errors.

Figure 2: WAVE browser extension showing accessibility errors, alerts, and structure of the page.

- Lighthouse: An open-source tool built into Chrome DevTools, offering automated audits for performance, SEO, and accessibility. It

provides scores along with categorized suggestions to improve the website.

Figure 3. Google Lighthouse audit panel showing accessibility score and detailed report.

3.3 Procedure

To begin the study, a short online session was conducted by the researcher to introduce participants to the concept of web accessibility. This session covered the importance of making websites accessible for users with disabilities and briefly discussed common accessibility issues that affect usability and inclusion.

Following the introduction, participants were guided through the installation process for each tool (WAVE, Axe DevTools, and Lighthouse). Basic usage instructions were provided — including how to initiate scans and where to view the reports — but no detailed training was given on interpreting the results, in order to simulate the experience of non-expert or first-time users. The goal was to assess how intuitive and user-friendly each tool is without external support.

Participants were then instructed to use each tool to evaluate a selected website (e.g., a university portal or public government site) and complete a structured online survey. The survey included both quantitative

Likert-scale questions (e.g., ease of use, confidence in understanding results) and open-ended questions (e.g., most difficult part, recommendations for improvement).

4. RESULT

To assess the usability and effectiveness of three web accessibility evaluation tools—WAVE, Axe, and Lighthouse—a survey was conducted among participants with varying degrees of technical expertise.

Table 1: Participant Background Summary

Participant id	Field of Study / Profession	Web Dev Experience	Accessibility Tool Experience	Aware of Accessibility Testing
P1	Student	Basic	No	No
P2	—	Significant	No	No
P3	Software Testing / CS	Basic	No	Yes
P4	CS	Basic	No	Yes
P5	Full Stack Developer	Significant	Yes	Yes
P6	MCA	Basic	Yes	Not Sure
P7	Computer Science	Basic	Yes	Yes
P8	Computer Science	Significant	No	Yes

This table presents the demographic background and relevant technical experience of the participants involved in the study. It includes information such as their field of study or profession, prior web development experience, and familiarity with accessibility testing tools and concepts. This helps provide context to their responses and perspectives on the accessibility tools evaluated in the research.

The results are categorized into five key areas:

1. Tool Installation and Accessibility

Most participants found the installation process for all three tools relatively easy. WAVE scored the highest in terms of initial accessibility, with the majority rating it 5/5 for ease of access. Axe and Lighthouse were also rated positively, though a few respondents noted that Axe required familiarity with browser developer tools.

2. Report Comprehension and Usability

WAVE was consistently described as userfriendly, particularly by non-technical participants. Its visual representation of issues directly on the web page was

seen as intuitive. In contrast, Axe’s reports were found to be more technical, making them less approachable for users without a development background. Lighthouse’s audit results were generally understood but were considered less detailed compared to the other tools.

3. Confidence in Interpreting Results

Confidence in interpreting accessibility issues was highest for WAVE and lowest for Axe. Participants with computer science backgrounds reported moderate to high confidence using all three tools, while non-technical users struggled more with technical jargon and implementation suggestions, particularly from Axe and Lighthouse.

Table 2: Tool Ease of Use Ratings (Average Scores)

Tool	Installation	Report Clarity	Confidence in Understanding	Overwhelming Interface
WAVE	4.3	4.3	4.1	Mixed (Some said "Yes")
Axe	4.4	4.1	4.1	Mixed (More said "Yes")
Lighthouse	4.2	4.25	4.1 (where available)	Mostly "No" (least overwhelming)

This table presents the average ease-of-use ratings for WAVE, Axe, and Lighthouse across four key dimensions: installation ease, clarity of reports, user confidence in understanding the issues, and whether users felt overwhelmed by the interface. While all three tools scored similarly in clarity and confidence, WAVE and Axe showed slightly higher perceptions of being overwhelming compared to Lighthouse, which was generally seen as more straightforward and less intimidating.

4. Recommendation for Non-Technical Users WAVE was overwhelmingly recommended for nontechnical users due to its visual feedback and minimal reliance on code knowledge. Axe, while powerful, was largely seen as better suited for developers. Lighthouse received mixed reviews; while some appreciated its simplicity, others desired more detailed guidance.

Table 3: User Recommendation to Non-Technical People

Tool	Recommended to Non-Technical?	Common Reasons Given
WAVE	Yes (6 of 8 users)	Easy visuals, simple language
Axe	No (6 of 8 users)	Technical terms, less friendly
Lighthouse	Mixed	Depends on understanding level

This table summarizes user opinions on whether accessibility testing tools are suitable for nontechnical individuals. The majority of participants recommended WAVE due to its user-friendly interface, visual cues, and simplified explanations. In contrast, most users did not recommend Axe, citing the use of technical jargon and a less approachable layout. Lighthouse received mixed feedback, with some users noting that its usefulness for non-technical individuals largely depends on their familiarity with web concepts and ability to interpret summarized audit results.

5. Key Challenges and Suggestions

Participants highlighted common challenges, such as:

- Difficulty understanding technical terminology in Axe and Lighthouse
- Lack of actionable steps for fixing issues
- Interface overwhelm, especially when too many issues were listed

Suggestions included:

- Simplified language in reports
- Step-by-step remediation guides
- More visual examples and explanations
- Interface redesigns to prioritize critical issues

Table 4: Challenges Reported & Suggested Improvements

Tool	Challenges Faced	Suggestions from Participants
WAVE	Understanding icons/terms	Clearer descriptions, simpler language
Axe	Technical format, DevTools confusion	Non-tech guide, visual examples
Lighthouse	Overwhelming details, prioritization	Simplified reports, actionable step-by-step fixes

This table presents the most commonly reported challenges users faced while using accessibility tools, along with their suggestions for improvement. Key difficulties included interpreting technical terminology, understanding how to act on reported issues, and feeling overwhelmed by dense interfaces. Suggested improvements focused on simplifying language, providing clearer guidance or visual examples, and offering step-by-step solutions or interactive tutorials to better support nontechnical users.

5. Conclusion

This study sought to evaluate the usability of WAVE, Axe, and Lighthouse for accessibility testing, particularly from the perspective of non-technical users. The results demonstrate that WAVE is the most accessible and user-friendly tool, providing clear, visual feedback that can be understood without deep technical knowledge. Axe and Lighthouse, while robust in detection capability, present challenges in comprehension and actionability for less experienced users.

The implications of these findings are significant for developers, educators, and tool designers. For educators, WAVE can serve as an introductory tool in web development and accessibility courses. For tool developers, this study highlights the need to simplify report language, offer guided tutorials, and design interfaces that reduce cognitive load. Accessibility tools should not only detect issues but also empower all users—regardless of technical skill—to resolve them.

Limitations of this study include the sample size and the technical familiarity of most participants. Future research should explore broader user groups, including complete novices, and focus on real-world issue resolution effectiveness across different website types.

6. REFERENCES

1. S. Harper and Y. Yesilada, "Emerging technologies and web accessibility: research challenges and opportunities focussing on vision issues...", "Disabil Rehabil Assist Technol.", Vol.7, pp. 1-19, 2012.
2. W3C WAI. Introduction to web accessibility. <http://www.w3.org/WAI/intro/accessibility.php,2005>.
3. Yesilada et al. (2011) explored overlapping challenges faced by both disabled individuals and mobile users, finding that many barriers—such as small screens or poor navigation—affect both groups similarly.
4. Arch (2009) emphasized the need for improved accessibility features for aging web users, discussing key progress made and the gaps that still need attention.

5. Section 508 standards. Access Board of the U.S. Federal Government.
<http://www.section508.gov/>.
6. <https://wave.webaim.org/> [last access date: 05 April 2025].
7. Deque Systems. Axe DevTools – Accessibility Testing Tools for Developers.
<https://www.deque.com/axe/devtools/> [Last accessed: 05 April 2025].
8. Google Developers. Lighthouse – OpenSource, Automated Tool for Improving the Quality of Web Pages.
<https://developer.chrome.com/docs/lighthouse/> [Last accessed: 05 April 2025]
9. Nguyen, T. (2022). Evaluating Automated Accessibility Checker Tools. Western Washington University, Western CEDAR.
10. According to Abuaddous et al. (2018), challenges in web accessibility span across design, development, and evaluation phases, especially due to low developer awareness and over-reliance on automated tools.
11. Kelly, B., Nevile, L., Sloan, D., Fanou, S., Ellison, R., & Herrod, L. (2009). From Web Accessibility to Web Adaptability. Proceedings of the W4A 2009 International Cross-Disciplinary Conference on Web Accessibility.